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Weber as ENVIRONMENTALIST: conceptual relation to NATURE.

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The social science in the modern scheme does not attend the human relationship to nature from an analytic view point, neither from the moral approach. When done, it is from a positive perspective, or as a reaffirming factor of personal realization: that is as *means*.

Both in its epistemological and ontological dimension, nature is a mere stage, background curtain, surrounding, scope of concurrency of the human action.

Every sociologic project for the understanding of the human realm, as diverse as they may be- (Derrida, Ocepec, Stračević, Marx, Weber, Durkheim) they all share the theoretical coordinates of *modernity*, specifically of the *Illustration movement* which is thegnoseological support of socialism, capitalism and liberalism, whether as economic or political proposals.

The objective here, is to endow NATURE of value itself, with the same status the *Illustration* assigns to man as *end* not as *means*.

For Weber (2016,1961) the human world evolves through the principle of reason. He grants an active role to nature at the basis of the social order in modern societies but a much greater influence in social conducts and institutions of the ancient world and the simpler societies of the Neolithic and especially the pre-Neolithic age. For methodologic purposes, he draws upon 'ideal types' as an abstract model of analysis in where NATURE emerges as a –major or minor- influence factor as progress is made from simple and organic, to complex and inorganic societies, of which the modern industrial society is the most general and abstract level, -beyond disciplinary shortcuts- in which nature is the primal foundation of all life forms, human and nonhuman. The society-nature relationship conducted in this manner, from the outside of modern society, could be a pathological one; seen from within, it is only natural, positive and reassuring: science and technology are multipurpose in the narrative of modernity, but are fundamentally cultivated as a method to discipline nature. Both set nature at its utmost condition to be exploitable by the capital and be regulated by the market. It is the market by whose laws, of offer and demand, that decides its destiny, its utility, and the magnitude in which it is required to satisfy the needs of production for consumption, in other words, the level, degree and intensity of its own destruction. This submission leads to

destruction and self-destruction, and through the same path to the denial of modernity, and its material foundations.

Along the decade of the sixties, a number of changes took place in the West mainly cultural, a new sensibility questioning the values of a modern society which was starting to notice the exhaustion of a life model based in the search of values and material gratifications, personal accomplishments, economic success, and social mobility all conceived under the model of natural selection. In the environmental field, this cultural and regulatory change is encouraged by the birth of a new perception of planet Earth as vulnerable, fragile, small, and solitary in the vastness of the universe stimulated from the images sent from outer space –among other things-.

The environmental, as an effect of the crisis, is posed as a problem, and starts to be part of a concept, part of the regulation of quality of life, is made object of consciousness and vindication. In his way, the environmental damage is made visible, it emerges as background noise, it starts to have social resonance and this is linked to changes that have to do with the ways of modernity, with the transition to a more reflective society, a society that begins to be fully modern because it applies to itself the *modern* principles, that radicalizes *modernity*, that goes into crisis because of the collateral effects of such modernity, and not only receives these collateral damage on itself, but also starts a real self-reflection period, of questioning, to see as problem what before was not seen as such, but was rather considered as the base and need of progress: this is the domination and submission for human ends, which ends up with its depletion and exhaustion. Finally, the destruction of the natural grounds of modern society and any social order.

This change of values makes new social norms emerge, a new notion of what quality of life and well-being is, opposite of the materialistic values of the industrial modern society.

Epistemologically, the devastation of the natural world emerges as a fact of consciousness, as a reality check mediated by the symbolic representation of devastation and its translation to an idea of well-being, of quality of life that fades away, as a consequence, of the crisis caused by the environmental damage, which emerges in our consciousness as a result of the spawning of cultural, evaluative and normative changes that make this idea possible, sometimes insinuating itself, others showing itself quite clearly.

This process does not only occur as a fact of consciousness, it also happens in the real world, ontologically, in the modern world, and starts building up as an ethical problem as well as an analytical reflection.

How can this utilitarian vision twirl into an interest in *NATURE* as end not means?

- a. How can it be made sustainable?
- b. How can it substantiate an ethic system that values *NATURE* for what is, for itself?

This scope broadens, opening the way for other social actors, and opens the anthropocentric to other fields.

The crisis operates as a kind of dream that works as a scenario for *NATURE* to express its voice, its “truth”, its being-in-the-world, if we can think the relationship from the ‘active’ side of *NATURE*. This situates this critique “out” of modernity, because it is only the crisis of modern society, in its moments of break down, in its fragmented aspects, in its moments of distraction, during its lapses, or failed paces, when some of these moments make it possible to set off its epistemological and ontological limits, and thus enable society, on the one hand, to think this relationship from a critical perspective. Only in those elapsed moments, when *modernity* dreams, while its guardians sleep, when they suffer from drowsiness, can nature insinuate its secrets, its regrets, its true relationship with the nonhuman: the pathologic relationship. On the other hand, the same crisis opens the way for nature to express its own being, its essence, a plausible communication from the nonhuman towards the human.

A sort of Copernican revolution awaits to see with other eyes and transcend the dominative and submissive relationship of the nonhuman by the *modern* human being. Both man and society can be seen in their dramatic need of nature and the nonhuman world. As well as under the opposite relationship: nature in need of the humane, to the same extent nature needs of the other species to survive, to constitute and diversify in its complexity; even more to the extent that human consciousness, also in evolution, could also be assumed as awareness of nature itself, nature made awareness, possibility, responsibility, human commitment to nature, with the planet and the nonhuman, nature that takes care of itself, vigilant agent of the planetary life system maintenance which the modern relationship to nature threatens and undermines. This twirl is a safe foundation to build on the *OIKOS*.

In this sense, anthropology is the scope that opens the door to the trip back ‘outside’, to the other, it can make contact or be more sensitive to the irrational, with that enchanted world that rationality can annihilate, but whose persistence indicates the inherent constitutive character of human action: it is here where *NATURE* has space, where the nonhuman claims that which *modernity* has denied: its reality status with intrinsic value, as an expressive reality, in need of

communication with the human, it appears everywhere, it revolts everywhere, it rebels in its need to be, of being known epistemically and morally; it rebels to the civilizing process, and even more with actual globalization stage. From the analytic view point, it is the nonhuman trying, forcing, intending communication with the human world. From the ethic standing point –nature: the nonhuman- emerging as end with value for itself.

Art also opens a door to knowledge, it generates the conditions of possibility, and enables to step out of the logics of the modern, even more out of the rational: from another field, from a sort of exteriority, opens a path of unconventional access, of knowledge and communication with the nonhuman, with the not-modern, non-rational human.

This crisis of modernity has left uncovered the insufficiency of the concepts on which it was founded, its destructive development: it requires not only a change of values but an extension of the principles by which we think of inequality and exploitation among humans, the submission of nature, and its concept of sole provider of raw materials or natural resources as supplies for an economy far away from the human, distanced from the same human objectives. A change of relationship that suppresses the value of change, the market, and the economy as the regulatory principle with NATURE.

Weber did think about NATURE due to the central role this concept played in the scientific thought of his time, also because it's intervention and appropriation was crucial technologically and economically speaking for the ends of the modern capitalist society.

Nevertheless, this does not mean they had the environmentalist scope as it is understood today, even more since we have tied its value as *end* rather than *means*, therefore we think of nature as an influential factor to social action, and on the other hand, it deserves moral consideration and environmental consciousness to face of its devastation and its utilitarian and instrumental usage. Only in isolated moments and not in a systematic manner does Weber gives way to certain ideas close to the contemporary sense of the concept of environmental nature.

On one side, an epistemological exclusion accounts for the inability of Weber's sociologic theory to see nature's exploitation and decay, is a result of the modern capitalist relationship which is built through the concept of market *exchange value*, within economics.

As nature is subdued to the production of goods, commodified, governed by the logic of the infinite demand (human and nonhuman) being essentially limited and finite, it ends up devastated.

On the other side, we sustain that this exclusion of nature, its exploitation, and devastation is also ontological to the extent that it is a constitutive part of modern society which in its capitalist version cannot exist without its support to the market which outcomes as destruction.

For Weber, the epistemological exclusion is clear and explicit as he does not consider it as a determinant factor in social action. Nature for him, has no meaning nor purpose, so is reduced to the unknown into the irrational realm. This fact logically leads us to the ontological exclusion at the base which can be inferred from the differential role, he assigns to nature in pre-modern organic societies and the modern inorganic ones. In modern industrial societies, the submission of nature, the human ability to manipulate, mold and use it for its own objectives, builds modern man, modern society and cuts loose the different natural factors which enable the modern human to exercise “full freedom” and “free will”¹.

Which is more of a bully attitude towards nature.

If we understand NATURE, in its full ecosystemic existence, its independence and self-value, we must conclude classic sociologists hardly thought of it that way. The administration of the OIKOS is one sided towards the human need's satisfaction rather than the sustainability of the system in the long run. Therefore, they were incapable of anticipating the consequences that nature's devastation has carried along as the contemporary crisis has dramatically showed in so many aspects that today we fear for our existence. No crisis of that in time, considering the importance it might have had at that moment, can be compared to the magnitude of the present one, because the scientific and technologic development has strengthened the human capacity of massive and intense economic appropriation of nature, the struggle for markets, labor force, raw materials, consumers worldwide, have created the condition for a devastation without precedents, inexistent at the Weber time.

¹ In Marx, the valuation process is the core of capitalism, merchandise, surplus value and gain are produced inside the system, therefore works as the invisibility mechanism that excludes the exploitation of nature as the core of the modern capitalist.

On the other hand, this environmental contemporary crisis (especially with COVID 19), hatched by modern thought, has caused the `eye-opening` effect worldwide of the sociologic view over the magnitude of nature's destruction, over its constitutive link to failed *modernity* of its reasons and most deep causes, of the modern values that produced and sustains such havoc. But most importantly, the pressing need of a change of the value system in cultural and material terms to enable the coexistence of any human project, which may build dialogue. A coexistence not mutually destructive that won't destroy either the human nor the non-human element, that is constructive, that can co-generate life: both social and natural life.

Personally, I would like to clearly state that for this re-valuation to take place we must:

1. Reinstall a healthy **ontology** open to all beings, where every single one of them has a place: Nature has showed that is how healthy ecosystems thrive.
2. This shall lead us to a safe **epistemology** and keep our heads closer to nature and discover it at is full, permitting ourselves be endowed with the awesome.
3. This may reassure an **ethical** relationship with our fellows and honor with gratitude every element that has made life possible, and as humbly and harmonically try to reproduce natures ways and models with respect and no destruction.

Thank you.